

A Holistic Approach in Cure of Eczema Through Homoeopathy

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Abstract

Introduction: Eczema are group of etiologically unrelated condition that have similar clinical morphology, having ICD code L30.8.^[1] Eczema in Greek means to boil over^[2]. It is defined as pattern of skin inflammation that has characteristic morphologies in acute, sub acute & chronic phases^[3].

Acute phase: Erythema, oedema, vesiculation, oozing & crusting.

Subacute phase: Erythematous, hyperpigmented plaques with scaling & crusting.

Chronic phase: Lichenification

All eczemas are dermatitis but all dermatitis are not eczema. Histopathologically this group of condition is typified by epidermal intercellular oedema (spongiosis).

Etiological grouping of eczema^[4]: Exogenous eczema: An external cause for the eczema is identifiable and when this is removed, eczema doesn't recur. E.g., Irritant dermatitis, allergic contact dermatitis, photodermatitis. Endogenous eczema: An internal cause or an inherent property of the skin is responsible for occurrence of eczema. E.g., Atopic dermatitis, pityriasis alba, seborrheic dermatitis, discoid eczema, asteotic eczema, gravitational eczema, lichen simplex chronicus, prurigo nodularis.

Clinical stages of eczema: It evolves through 3 stages^[5]: Acute eczema: intense itching, erythema, oedema papilovesicles, oozing. Subacute eczema: erythema (lesser), crusting, scaling, fissuring, slight to moderate itching, stinging & burning sensation. Chronic eczema: Dryness of skin, excoriation, fissuring, lichenification.

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Homoeopathic remedies for eczema often focuses on addressing the individuals overall health, skin symptoms ,and underlying causes like allergies or stress.

Conclusion: Individualized homoeopathic treatment has good scope in treating skin diseases. Through holistic approach, homoeopathy not only found to be effective to improve the physical symptoms but also improved mental wellbeing of patient.

Case study of Eczema

Name: - Mr. XYZ

Occupation: - Sugar factory worker and farmer

Age: - 41 years male

DOB: - 11/06/1984

K/c/o: - Dry Eczema

Weight: - 71 kg

Presenting complaints: -

Dry scaly eruption on ankle since 1.5 years, Itching+3, Scaly, dry skin, wants to Scratch until it bleeds also, he wants to scratch a with nails.

<Winter/ cold air, >on applying water.

Past history: - eruptions On Neck and ear in 2018 allopathy taken and relieved

Family history: - Father HTN Since 1 year on Rx allopathy

Habit –Betel nut

Diet: - Mixed

Appetite: - Normal

Desire: - Meat

Aversion- Sweet +3

Thirst: - LQLI, Thirsty

Urine: -Satisfactory, no any complaints

Perspiration: - Whole body. Only on exertion

Sleep: -Sound

Dreams: - Not remembered

Bowel: -Constipation

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Repertorial totality: -

1. Graphites – 15/9
2. Arsenicum album -15/7
3. Lycopodium – 14/7

Selection of Remedy: - Graphites

Prescription: - Graphites 30 stat – 4 globules (30 no. globules)
 Pl – 3 globules TDS for 15 days (40 no. globules)

Follow up: -

Date	Symptoms	Prescription
16/9/2025		Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
30/9/2025	 Itching +++ , Eruptions ++	Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days

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15/10/2025		Graphite 30 stat Pl for 15 days
30/10/2025	<p data-bbox="525 1205 1125 1279">Itching +++, Eruptions appear on anterior side also</p>	Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
15/11/2025		Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
30/11/2025	Itching reduced upto 40 %	Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days

15/12/2025		Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
30/12/2025	<p style="text-align: center;">Itching reduced upto 60 %</p>	Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
15/1/2026		Graphites 30 stat Pl for 15 days
30/1/2026	No itching and eruptions present	Pl for 15 days

Miasmatic background: Sycosis is the dominant miasm in given case.^[8]

Hahnemannian viewpoints^[9] :-

If the physician clearly perceives what is to be cured in diseases, that is to say, in every individual case of disease (knowledge of disease, indication), if he clearly perceives what is curative in medicines, that is to say, in each individual medicine (knowledge of medical powers), and if he knows how to adapt, according to clearly defined principles, what is curative in medicines to what he has discovered to be undoubtedly morbid in the patient, so that the recovery must ensue

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adapt it, as well in respect to the suitability of the medicine most appropriate according to its mode of action to the case before him (choice of the remedy, the medicine indicated), as also in respect to the exact mode of preparation and quantity of it required (proper dose), and the proper period for repeating the dose; if, finally, he knows the obstacles to recovery in each case and is aware how to remove them, so that the restoration may be permanent, then he understands how to treat judiciously and rationally, and he is a true practitioner of the healing art. According to aphorism 3 of organon of medicine Dr.Hahnemann emphasizes on what should be cured in disease.

This holds good to such an extent, that the state of the disposition of the patient often chiefly determines the selection of the homoeopathic remedy, as being a decidedly characteristic symptom, which can least of all remain concealed from the accurately observing physician.

According to aphorism 211 special attention should be given to mental and general symptoms.

It is not useful, either in acute local diseases of recent origin or in local affections that have already existed a long time, to rub in or apply externally to the spot an external remedy, even though it be the specific and, when used internally, salutary by reason of its homoeopathically, even although it should be at the same time administered internally; for the acute topical affections (e.g., inflammations of the individual parts, erysipelas, etc.), which have not been caused by external injury of proportionate violence, but by dynamic or internal causes, yield most surely to internal remedies homoeopathically adapted to the perceptible state of the health present in the exterior and interior, selected from the general store of proved medicines, 1 and generally without any other aid; but if these diseases do not yield to them completely, and if there still remain in the affected spot and in the whole state, notwithstanding good regimen, a relic of disease which the vital force is not competent to restore to the normal state, then the acute disease was (as not infrequently happens) a product of psora which had hitherto remained latent in the interior, but has now burst forth and is on the point of developing into a palpable chronic disease.

In aphorism 194 Dr. Hahnemann states that the physician should not remove external symptoms by local applications since they are part of whole diseases.

Discussion: - The case of dry eczema treated with Graphites 30C demonstrates the application of classical homoeopathic principles as laid down in Hahnemann's organon of medicine.

The present case highlights the importance of constitutional treatment to address the internal disturbance rather than merely the cutaneous expression.

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The choice of 30C potency was made considering the chronic yet moderate intensity of the disease, absence of irreversible pathological changes, and presumed patient susceptibility. Hahnemann underscores that the remedy must be administered in the smallest possible dose sufficient to effect a gentle cure (Aphorism 246). Furthermore, Aphorism 275 warns against unnecessarily large doses that may produce medicinal aggravation. A medium potency such as 30C often serves as an appropriate starting point in chronic functional disorders where vitality is adequate and pathology is not advanced.

Regarding repetition, the remedy was administered as a single dose and repeated at 15-day intervals based on clinical assessment. This approach is consistent with Aphorism 245, which states that as long as improvement continues, repetition of the remedy is unnecessary. Over-frequent repetition can interfere with the curative process and produce avoidable aggravation (Aphorism 276). The interval-based repetition in this case reflects adherence to the “wait and watch” principle, allowing the vital force to respond to the dynamic stimulus without undue interference.

Conclusion: Individualized homoeopathic treatment has good scope in treating skin diseases. Through holistic approach, homoeopathy not only found to be effective to improve the physical symptoms but also improved mental wellbeing of patient.

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